

Some New Schiffs Bases Derived from Vanillin as Possible Anticonvulsants

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Manuscript received 29 February 1980, revised 28 October 1980, accepted 28 January 1981

Twenty new anilino-[3-methoxy-4-(4-aryl-1-piperazinoacetoxy)] benzylidenes a ten anilino-[3-methoxy-4-{3-mercapto-4-aryl-1,2,4(H)-triazol-5-yl} methyleneoxy] benzylidenes were synthesised. Seven of these compounds when screened for anticonvulsant activity against maximal electro shock seizures and pentylenetetrazole induced seizures in mice at a dose of 80 mg/kg were found to be inactive.

MONOAMINE oxidase inhibitors have been known to possess pronounced anticonvulsant activity¹. Some benzylidene derivatives have recently shown psychotropic properties² and inhibited *in vitro* M.A.O. activity³ of rat brain homogenates. Also several piperazine derivatives have been reported as anticonvulsants⁴⁻⁹. Furthermore, 1-phenyl 1,2,4(H)-triazole¹⁰ and mercaptotriazoles¹¹ are also found to exhibit anticonvulsant properties. Hence, the synthesis of above benzylidenes was undertaken. The steps involved in the synthesis are sketched in Scheme I.

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel.

Substituted anilino-(3-methoxy-4-chloroacetoxy)-benzylidenes (IVa) :

These were prepared by the method of Parmar *et al*⁸.

IVa, R=OC₂H₅, m.p.=104-5° (Yiel 80%).
Found : N 3.92% C₁₈H₁₈NO₄Cl requires N 4.02%

Substituted anilino-[3-methoxy-4-(4-aryl-1 piperazinoacetoxy)]benzylidenes (A) :

A mixture of a substituted anilino-(3-methoxy-4-chloroacetoxy)benzylidene (0.005 M) and a suitable aryl piperazine (0.01 M) in dry benzene (25 ml) was refluxed on a steam bath for 6-8 hr. Excess of benzene was distilled off. The solid mass thus separated was collected by filtration, dried and recrystallised from methanol. The benzylidenes so obtained were characterised by their sharp m.p., elemental analysis and appearance of ir spectral bands at 1410-1420 cm⁻¹ (C-N-aliph).

Anilino - [3-methoxy-4 - {3-mercapto-4-aryl-1,2,4-(H)-triazol-5-yl} methyleneoxy]benzylidenes (B) :

A mixture of an appropriate anilino-[3-methoxy-4-(4-aryl thiosemicarbazidocarbonylmethyleneoxy)]benzylidene (0.01 M), sodium methylate (0.011 M) and absolute methanol (25 ml) was heated under reflux for 12 hr. The solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure. The residue obtained was added with stirring to an ice cold water containing conc. HCl, when a flocculent precipitate of the thiol was

Scheme 1

obtained. It was washed successively with cold water and 50% aq. acetic acid and finally recrystallised from glacial acetic acid as reddish crystals. The compounds thus prepared were characterised by their m.p. and analysis (Table 4).

The structures of the above compounds were supported by the disappearance of a peak at 1680 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{O}$ of the sec. amide) found in the corresponding thiosemicarbazido benzylidenes (Table 2, IX to XVIII).

TABLE 1—SUBSTITUTED ANILINO-(3-METHOXY-4-SUBSTITUTED)BENZYLIDENES*

Compd.	R	M	m.p. °C	Yield %	Formula	Nitrogen%	
						Calcd.	Found
III	Cl	H	128	85	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}_2\text{Cl}$	5.35	5.02
IV	OC_2H_5	H	102	80	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_2$	5.16	4.98
V	Cl	$\text{CH}_2\text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5$	70	80	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{NO}_4\text{Cl}$	4.02	4.32
VI	OC_2H_5	$\text{CH}_2\text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5$	101-5	78	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{22}\text{NO}_5$	3.92	3.71
VII	Cl	$\text{CH}_2\text{CONHNH}_2$	198-99	60	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$	12.59	12.32
VIII	OC_2H_5	$\text{CH}_2\text{CONHNH}_2$	168-70	62	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$	12.24	12.02

* Prepared by a reported procedure^{1,2}.

TABLE 2—SUBSTITUTED ANILINO-[3-METHOXY-4-(4-ARYL THIOSEMICARBAZIDOCARBONYLMETHYLENEXOXY)]-BENZYLIDENES*

Compd.	R	Ar	m.p. °C	Yield %	Formula	Nitrogen%	
						Calcd.	Found
IX	Cl	C_6H_5	145-46	80	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_4\text{O}_5\text{SCl}$	11.95	11.72
X	Cl	$3\text{-CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	226	75	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_4\text{O}_5\text{SCl}$	11.60	11.38
XI	Cl	$4\text{-CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	190	70	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_4\text{O}_5\text{SCl}$	11.60	11.20
XII	Cl	$4\text{-ClC}_6\text{H}_4$	180	80	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}_5\text{SCl}_2$	11.13	11.32
XIII	Cl	$4\text{-OC}_2\text{H}_5\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	168-70	73	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{25}\text{N}_4\text{O}_5\text{SCl}$	10.92	10.72
XIV	OC_2H_5	C_6H_5	156-58	78	$\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_4\text{O}_5\text{S}$	11.71	11.45
XV	OC_2H_5	$3\text{-CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	216	70	$\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{25}\text{N}_4\text{O}_5\text{S}$	11.38	11.10
XVI	OC_2H_5	$4\text{-CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	230	80	$\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{25}\text{N}_4\text{O}_5\text{S}$	11.38	11.18
XVII	OC_2H_5	$4\text{-ClC}_6\text{H}_4$	166	81	$\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_4\text{O}_5\text{SCl}$	10.92	10.74
XVIII	OC_2H_5	$4\text{-OC}_2\text{H}_5\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	160	70	$\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_4\text{O}_5\text{S}$	10.72	10.48

* Prepared by a published procedure^{1,2}.

TABLE 3—ANILINO-[3-METHOXY-1-(4-ARYL-1-PIPERAZINO ACETOXY)] BENZYLIDENES (CORRESPONDING TO A)

Sl. No.	R	R ¹	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	Nitrogen%	
					Calcd.	Found
1.*	Cl	<i>m</i> -Cl	204	$\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{25}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3\text{Cl}_2$	8.43	8.12
2.*	CH_3	<i>m</i> -Cl	200	$\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3\text{Cl}$	8.79	8.48
3.	OC_2H_5	<i>m</i> -Cl	200	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$	8.27	8.12
4.	OCH_3	<i>m</i> -Cl	192-94	$\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$	8.51	8.32
5.*	OC_2H_5	<i>p</i> -Cl	268	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$	8.27	8.48
6.	Cl	<i>p</i> -Cl	240	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2$	8.43	8.25
7.*	OCH_3	<i>p</i> -Cl	238	$\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$	8.51	8.35
8.	CH_3	<i>p</i> -Cl	256	$\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$	8.79	8.34
9.	Cl	<i>p</i> - CH_3	110-12	$\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$	8.79	8.53
10.	OCH_3	<i>p</i> - CH_3	204-206	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{31}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4$	8.87	8.62
11.	OC_2H_5	<i>p</i> - CH_3	230	$\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{33}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4$	8.62	8.31
12.	CH_3	<i>p</i> - CH_3	226	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{31}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4$	9.19	9.40
13.	CH_3	<i>m</i> - CH_3	156	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{31}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4$	9.19	9.32
14.	OCH_3	<i>m</i> - CH_3	140	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{31}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4$	8.87	8.82
15.	OC_2H_5	<i>m</i> - CH_3	190	$\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{33}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4$	8.62	8.36
16.	Cl	<i>m</i> - CH_3	162	$\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$	8.79	8.85
17.	Cl	H	246	$\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$	9.06	9.94
18.	OC_2H_5	H	244	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{31}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4$	8.87	8.39
19.	OCH_3	H	240	$\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{29}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4$	9.15	9.36
20.	CH_3	H	240	$\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{29}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4$	9.48	9.13

Yield ranged from 50-70%.

* Screened for anticonvulsant activity.

TABLE 4—ANILINO-[3-METHOXY-4-(3-MERCAPTO-4-ARYL-1,2,4(H)-TRIAZOL-5-YL)METHYLENEOXY]-BENZYLIDENES (CORRESPONDING TO B)

Sl. No.	R	Ar	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	Nitrogen%	
					Calcd.	Found
1.	OC ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	164	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	12.17	12.88
2.	Cl	C ₆ H ₅	250	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₂ SCl	12.43	12.65
3.	Cl	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	270(sublimes)	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₂ SCl	12.05	11.98
4.	Cl	3-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	262	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₂ SCl	12.05	11.94
5.	OC ₂ H ₅	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	110-12	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	11.81	11.56
6.*	Cl	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	168-70	C ₂₈ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ SCl ₂	11.54	11.32
7.*	Cl	4-OC ₂ H ₅ C ₆ H ₄	240-42	C ₂₈ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₂ SCl	11.32	11.12
8.*	OC ₂ H ₅	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	115-16	C ₂₈ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₂ SCl	11.32	11.48
9.	OC ₂ H ₅	4-OC ₂ H ₅ C ₆ H ₄	106-108	C ₂₇ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₂ S	11.11	11.32
10.	OC ₂ H ₅	3-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	160	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	11.81	11.62

Yield ranged from 50-60%.

* Screened for anticonvulsant activity.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their sincere thanks to Prof. T. N. Srivastava, Head, Chemistry Department, Lucknow University for providing departmental facilities and to Dr. R. C. Srimal of C.D.R.I., Lucknow for anticonvulsant screening of the compounds. Thanks are also due to Dr. S. P. Tewarson, Principal, Lucknow Christian College for granting academic leave and to the U.G.C., New Delhi for providing teacher fellowship to one of us (G.C.S.).

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